

IMPROVING MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE TRADE

Turaboeva Feruza, student,
Fergana state university

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Abstract: Improving trade marketing is of great importance in the organization of targeted and continuous satisfaction of consumer demand for fruits and vegetables in countries around the world. In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to achieving economic growth through the coordination of trade and logistics, sales and storage of fruits and vegetables, the use of effective marketing strategies in doing business. In this regard, tasks such as "implementation of trade agreements in new target export markets", "marketing of products in domestic and target international markets and reduction of transportation costs" have been identified.

Key words: marketing of products, international trade, logistics, commercial marketing.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТОРГОВЛЯ ОВОЩАМИ

Аннотация: Совершенствование трейд-маркетинга имеет большое значение в организации целенаправленного и непрерывного удовлетворения потребительского спроса на плодоовощную продукцию в странах мира. В Узбекистане особое внимание уделяется достижению экономического роста за счет координации торговли и логистики, реализации и хранения фруктов и овощей, использования эффективных маркетинговых стратегий при ведении бизнеса. В связи с этим определены такие задачи, как «реализация торговых соглашений на новых целевых экспортных рынках», «сбыт продукции на внутреннем и целевых международных рынках и снижение транспортных расходов».

Ключевые слова: маркетинг продукции, международная торговля, логистика, коммерческий маркетинг.

MARKETING FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH SABZAVOT SAVDOSI

Annotatsiya: savdo marketingini takomillashtirish dunyo mamlakatlarida meva-sabzavot mahsulotlariga iste'molchilarning talabini maqsadli va doimiy ravishda qondirishni tashkil etishda katta ahamiyatga ega. O'zbekistonda savdo va logistikani muvofiqlashtirish, meva-sabzavotlarni sotish va saqlash, biznes yuritishda samarali marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanish orqali iqtisodiy o'sishga erishishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Shu munosabat bilan "yangi maqsadli eksport bozorlarida savdo bitimlarini amalga oshirish", "ichki va maqsadli xalqaro bozorlarda mahsulot sotish va transport xarajatlarini kamaytirish" kabi vazifalar belgilandi.

Kalit so'zlar: mahsulot marketingi, xalqaro savdo, logistika, tijorat marketingi.

INTRODUCTION

Improving trade marketing is of great importance in the organization of targeted and continuous satisfaction of consumer demand for fruits and vegetables in countries around the world. In the context of the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic, especially the regulation of the trading system is being studied as a major problem of socio-economic development in countries. According to the World Bank, international trade turnover "decreased by 0.1% in 2019, and in 2020 decreased by about 10.1% compared to 2019." The closure of borders and disruptions in the

supply of international goods and services, especially fruit and vegetable trade, pose a problem for finding innovative solutions in trade.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Infrastructural changes in the world commodity market, the emergence of modern trends in retail and wholesale trade, innovative activity of enterprises in the struggle for competition and consumer, as well as differences in their goals, interests, functions and processes require significant changes in modern trade marketing. Research is being conducted on the development of long-term and mutually beneficial cooperation strategies based on business relations between manufacturers, distributors, wholesalers and retailers, which are the main objects of trade marketing.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to achieving economic growth through the coordination of trade and logistics, sales and storage of fruits and vegetables, the use of effective marketing strategies in doing business. In this regard, tasks such as "implementation of trade agreements in new target export markets", "marketing of products in domestic and target international markets and reduction of transportation costs" have been identified. Effective implementation of these tasks includes the development of fruit and vegetable markets in trade marketing activities, improving the mechanisms for ensuring the interaction of growers, wholesalers and retailers of fruits and vegetables, further expanding the scope of research on the use of marketing strategies for relationship marketing and consumer value creation. is appropriate.

Changes in the infrastructure of the fruit and vegetable market, the emergence of innovative and unique areas of retail and wholesale trade, and the development of e-commerce require the use of innovative solutions in the competition for enterprises and the struggle for the buyer. Manufacturers are gaining competitiveness not only by innovations in the supply of goods, but also by the use of modern methods of delivery of goods to the final consumer (buyer), taking into account new ways to reduce costs in production and create value for customers to set low prices.

In this context, the need to increase efficiency through the development of long-term and mutually beneficial relations between fruit and vegetable producers, intermediaries, wholesalers and retailers based on the development of mutual business relations and joint planning of marketing activities has become a priority. The formation and development of "commercial marketing" as a new direction in the implementation of traditional marketing activities of enterprises is important in gaining a competitive advantage. Therefore, first of all, it is important to understand the interdependence of the concepts of "trade" and "trade marketing" and their content.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Trade is the main category of traditional classical marketing and is studied in the narrow sense as a form of commodity circulation, a form of exchange through the purchase and sale of labor products and services. In a broad sense, trade is understood as the most important area in the socio-economic development of the country, as an activity that drives the market, creates conditions for the creation of the process of commodity-money circulation. The formation and development of "trade marketing" enterprises as a new direction in the implementation of traditional marketing activities is important in a competitive environment.

Commercial marketing is used to varying degrees in modern marketing theories. In marketing theories there are 3 main stages in the development of "trade marketing": trade marketing (1970-1991), interactive trade marketing (1992-1999), strategic trade marketing (2000

to present). According to evolutionary development, although theories of trade marketing are considered as an old theory in the development trends of the world economy, its importance is observed to be more relevant within the consumer-oriented concept of marketing.

The use of trade marketing should be studied not only as a set of measures used to encourage the sale of products used by companies in the retail or wholesale trade, but also as a concept that involves the creation of value.

Theories of trade marketing are considered as a scientific problem that should be studied in international practice, from the concept of value creation for enterprises to the formation of a modern concept of consumer-oriented marketing, that is, the creation of value to the consumer. Based on this, the author argues that trade marketing is studied as a set of guaranteed cross-target market relations that provide value added to consumers in the processes that occur in the distribution of products across marketing channels.

The development trends of trade have shaped the transition from deals to relationships, as increased competition has led to the establishment of long-term mutually beneficial relationships between businesses, distributors, dealers, suppliers, as well as short-term operations. Trade marketing is studied as an activity in distribution channels, it is expedient to study the movement of goods and the flow of information from production to consumption, the satisfaction of end consumer needs, the interaction of participants in the distribution system aimed at increasing the final consumer value of goods through integrated business cooperation and marketing.

CONCLUSION

The value proposition is studied as a set of benefits provided to the participants of the distribution system to the consumers. In recent years, approaches to developing business models of value creation for consumers have become more relevant, as the success of an enterprise remains dependent on its ability to adapt its business to the needs of consumers.

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